

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MOFOLO****FIRST NAME: ROSALIA****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Steps for writing a good essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Structure of an academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-12)
3. Differences between US and UK English (EUCLID 2021, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
5. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)

WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I am excited to have come this far! I have been worried sick about how I will eventually get through this. I am used to responding to direct questions rather than simply reacting to the study materials, as requested for this response paper. Anyway, I read through the initial student orientation document to clearly understand the expectations of this course. After reviewing the study materials, I realized I needed a little reminder of what a good essay looks like! I found this very helpful as it highlighted what to do and not do to become successful. I took serious note of the common errors and mistakes to avoid, and these and the whole course are my primary references going forward. They will be my guide throughout the course and my everyday writing.

This response paper discusses the basic steps and the structure of writing an excellent academic paper. I also examine the main differences between US and UK English, the importance of plagiarism and how to avoid it, and style guides.

2) STEPS OF WRITING A GOOD ESSAY

A good plan goes a long way, even in academic writing. An academic essay presents responses to a set of questions the thesis seeks to answer (EUCLID 2021, 7). For this to happen, the writer must communicate very clearly. Before writing the essay, the student should follow a couple of basic steps. The steps include an early start to allow enough time to think and research the topic, otherwise known as the preparation phase (EUCLID 2021, 7; Scribbr, n.d.). This planning phase is helpful as it will enable one to fully understand the question and have a mental picture of what the essay will look like. Therefore, having a plan of what to include in the paper and what information to gather provides a reasonable basis for well-thought-out writing. Once one knows what to write about, the next critical step is reading more about the topic to understand the available literature and begin to collect information (EUCLID 2021, 8). There is absolutely no need to reinvent the wheel. I appreciated the advice on reading, where the first reading includes identifying information necessary for the topic (EUCLID 2021, 8-9). The next step involves ordering and arranging collected data to give it more structure and begin to outline the essay. This process includes reviewing the notes to select the information that supports the topic and has enough supporting evidence (EUCLID 2021, 9-10). Once one is sure of what to write about, the sequence of ideas, and enough supporting evidence, the next penultimate step is consolidating all facts into an outline of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10; Scribbr, n.d.). The following section explains this in detail. The last step after writing the paper is to ensure it is error-free, so proofreading is critical. One should carefully check the grammar, spelling, and punctuation as these are the usual culprits. I liked the idea of forgetting about the essay after writing it and only going back to review it with a ‘fresh perspective’ the next day (EUCLID 2021, 11).

3) STRUCTURE OF AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

Every essay should have some structure or format to help write and organize the paper. Scribbr and EUCLID (2021, 10) argue that any paper should have three essential parts: The introduction, main body, and conclusion. The introduction, as the word suggests, opens with a brief statement setting the tone for the essay. The idea here is to attract the reader’s attention, and the opening line should, therefore, be catchy to attract their attention and make them aware of what is coming (EUCLID 2021, 10).

The next phase is the main body – the most critical part of the essay. The body of the paper outlines the main arguments supporting the introduction. It follows and continues from the introduction by providing more evidence. According to Scribbr, the main body aims to provide, clarify, and analyze ideas alongside the data sources to support the case in the essay. It is where the writer interacts with all the information to demonstrate their knowledge and understanding of the topic (EUCLID 2021, 10). The student must organize the essay into paragraphs to have a well-defined structure. According to EUCLID (2021, 11) and Scribbr, each paragraph starts with a key or topic sentence that articulates the paragraph’s main idea. The rest of the other sentences in the paragraph expand the main

sentence. The Merriam-Webster dictionary explains a topic sentence as ‘a sentence that states the main thought of a section and is usually placed at or near the beginning.’

The final phase entails writing the conclusion. This is more like a concluding paragraph, which, according to EUCLID (2021, 10), ‘moves from specific to general.’ This is where the writer wraps up the discussion by reminding the reader about the topic and summarizing the key takeaways while avoiding introducing new information (EUCLID 2021, 10).

4) DIFFERENCES BETWEEN US AND UK ENGLISH

It was interesting to know why American English is the most powerful in the world today! I also learned that there are more similarities than differences between American and United Kingdom English (EUCLID 2021, 25). The marked difference is mainly in the spelling and punctuation. For instance, some words have exact spelling but different pronunciations and vice versa, commonly being *color* vs. *colour*, *center* vs. *centre*, and *licence* vs. *license* (EUCLID 2021, 25). Another notable difference I was unaware of is using single and double marks for quotation marks. I knew there were inverted commas and quotation marks but did not know that inverted commas have single marks and only apply to UK English. I knew that quotation marks refer to double marks, but I had no idea they only apply to US English (EUCLID 2021, 30-31). While it is acceptable to use any English version, I understand from this course that the most important thing is consistency - choosing one version and sticking to it throughout! Another important discovery about US English is that full stops and commas should always be inside the closing quotation marks (EUCLID 2021, 32).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is one of the worst academic offenses. Nevertheless, it is essential to understand plagiarism to appreciate why it is so unethical. I understand plagiarism as fraud or stealing someone’s ideas or work and passing it as your own (EUCLID 2021, 34). As a penalty, plagiarism can result in a student failing an examination or being expelled from school. Plagiarism manifests in many ways, including copying and pasting, quoting, and paraphrasing without acknowledging the author (EUCLID 2021, 34). The only way to avoid plagiarising is to ensure that one gives credit where it is due; that is the right and responsible thing to do. EUCLID (2021, 34-35) suggests two ways of proper citation: In-text citation and a list of cited sources. In-text is when one uses the author’s words verbatim in quotation marks or paraphrasing, while a list of cited sources is captured at the end of the paper to present the sources used.

6) STYLE GUIDES

I never knew that there was a “style guide.” A style guide is mainly about people’s writing styles; it is some standard or rule to be followed in academic writing to ensure consistency. Purdue University (2021) asserts that writing guidelines are not for referencing alone but also range from language and grammar use to font and size headings. For instance, EUCLID (2021, 41) prefers Chicago Rules (Turabian) and American English and has standard templates such as response and major papers and a quiz template. USAID has branding guidelines with specific colors and logos; the primary font is Gill Sans. I see the value here because a standard or uniformity is required where many partners and different people contribute to one document. This is one of the major problems in my organization since there are no writing guidelines; people write anyhow, making proofreading a nightmare.

In summary, style guides introduce uniformity across papers written by many people from different backgrounds. I now know what EUCLID is looking for and must adapt my writing style accordingly.

7) CONCLUSION

I have gained valuable information from this course. As an international paper, a Ph.D. thesis must conform to specific standards. For example, a good essay has an introduction, main body, and conclusion. The student needs to decide on the version of English and consistently use it. Of great importance is to observe academic integrity by avoiding plagiarizing and sticking to the stipulated style guides.

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